

TOYLABS

ENABLING AN OPEN INNOVATION MODEL FOR EU TOY INDUSTRY SMES
THROUGH CO-CREATION WITH FABLABS, SAFETY EXPERTS AND CUSTOMER
COMMUNITIES
732559

Final Dissemination Communication and Community Engagement Report

Deliverable No. 6.3		Final Dissemination Communication and Community Engagement Report	
WP No.	6	WP title	Dissemination Communication and Community Engagement
Activity No.	6.1 6.2 6.3	Activity Title	
Authors		AIJU	
Status (final, draft, revised draft)		Final	
Dissemination level		PU	
File Name		TOYLABS_AIJU_WP6_PUR_D6.3 FINAL DISSEMINATION COMMUNICATION AND COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT REPORT	

Version History Table

No.	Date	Author	Notes and Comments
0.1	21/05/18	AIJU	Initial ToC
0.2	7/06/18	AIJU	First Draft
0.3	15/06/18	AIJU	All partners Contribution added
0.35	18/06/18	NTUA	Scientific dissemination
0.4	22/06/18	AIJU	Final Draft
0.5	27/06/2018	AIJU	Synergies and Join activities with other Projects
0.6	28/06/18	SLG	Review and Additions
1.0	29/06/18	AIJU	Final Version for Submission

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ABBREVIATIONS LIST

Abbreviation	Meaning
KPI / KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SMEs	Small Medium Enterprises
WP	Work Package
MS	Milestone
D	Deliverable
M	Month
TSIG	TOYLABS Special Interest Group
AEFJ	Asociación Española de Fabricante de Juguetes
IoT	Internet of Things

ABSTRACT

The purpose of this deliverable is to report all the dissemination tools and activities developed and implemented in the project during the 2nd reporting period.

The report includes a description of all the activities including objectives, content and impact of each of them. In particular, ToyLabs communication and dissemination activities include:

- The ToyLabs public website that includes all the relevant information of the project including news and public deliverables. 1.371 visits in website.
- The newsletter created according with the main outcomes and milestones of the project. 9 newsletters published.
- Social media channels to reach a wide audience and engage potential stakeholders. 2950 followers
- The ToyLabs blog, published in the news section of the website, it includes blog posts related to the main outcomes of the project presenting the information in a more accessible way. 7 Blog posts published.
- Communication material: brochures, posters, promotional gifts, etc. to be brought at events, all created personalized to a specific target audience to meet their expectations. 2 brochures, 1 rollup, 3 promotional items.
- Organization of project events: 3 workshops and demo events.
- Participation in events: the partners in the consortium have attended and presented ToyLabs in many events. The main events include:
 - Spielwarenmesse 2018
 - Berlin Maker Faire 2018
- Scientific publications have been developed to disseminate the project among the scientific community. Publication of 3 conference papers.
- Various synergies with projects have been established including in some cases joint activities. 11 project with synergies and 3 joint activities.
- Description of the internal dissemination performed by each partner in their own organization network.

1 INTRODUCTION

The dissemination of the concept, activities and results of the Project is one of the most important phase of a research and innovation project. The main objective is to raise awareness of the project towards the interested stakeholders and properly communicate the results of the project.

To ensure the achievement of these objectives, several communication and dissemination tools have been developed. All the activities have been designed to ensure the proper communication of the project outcomes to the right audiences in the most effective way possible.

The report includes a profound description of all the undertaken activities including the objectives, content and impact of each action during the 2nd reporting period.

The following sections include the final report of the dissemination, communication and community engagement activities:

In section 2 Communication mechanisms the information contained is related to the ToyLabs website, Newsletter, Social Media, ToyLabs blog, traditional media and other communication materials.

Section 3 details de dissemination mechanisms including organization of project events, participation in events, scientific publications, community building and synergies with projects.

2 COMMUNICATION MECHANISMS

2.1 TOYLABS WEBSITE

The ToyLabs Website was created soon after the beginning of the project, it is available at <http://toylabs.eu/>

The toylabs.eu project website was built and is maintained by NTUA. The website's content is kept up to date by SILO and the website is also an entry point to the Toylabs platform which resides at <https://platform.toylabs.eu>.

Purpose

Nowadays, a public website represents one of the main communication media allowing a fast and accessible communication of any kind of information to a vast audience. An accessible website offers the possibility to any stakeholder to get in touch with the project and it allows to create awareness by having all the important information available and organized.

The website was designed in the most appropriate way to present all the public information in a clear and accessible manner, always having in mind the main search engines and a list of keywords to ensure the visibility.

This action had two main purposes: offer easy access to the relevant information of the project to create interest and facilitate the communication between interested stakeholders and the consortium.

For the first objective, all the public information has been displayed in the website including information about the project in general, the consortium, objectives of the project and work structure. To provide more in-depth information all public deliverables are available in the website. In addition, news and blogposts related to the progress of the project were also published in the website.

To ensure the easy communication with the consortium, the contact information is available on the website apart from links to the social media channels used.

Structure

ToyLabs' website is structured in different pages to offer clear and organised content. In the following each section and its content is briefly described

Figure 1 ToyLabs website Sections

As the first contact with any visitor, the Home Page offers a brief description of the basic information of the project. At the top there is a banner with some of the most relevant content in the website, as you scroll down you can find a brief description of the project scope, the consortium, links to the news and blogposts, the expected outcomes of the project, etc.

The contact page includes a contact form and the contact information, this page represents a direct and easy way to contact the consortium for those interested and get more information.

The news section represents a space where any relevant milestone or event is posted, it includes blogposts explaining different parts of the project and the progress on the different tasks and the newsletters. The blog posts and news have been created with the collaboration of all partners. In this section the visitor can really be aware of the evolution of the project in a more accessible manner.

The project info section explains with more detail the scope of the project explaining how ToyLabs will change the toy developing methodology by introducing a co creation platform with different actors. Here it is possible to find four subsections: consortium, deliverables, objectives/goal and work structure. In the consortium section you can find a description of the different organisations participating together to develop the project, it also includes a link to their organisation website. All the public deliverables form the project such as reports or demonstrable are available in a dedicated space, this way it is possible to get full information form the project development. In the objectives and goals section you can find in depth information about the scientific, technical and business objectives.

The next section is a special page dedicated to the ToyLabs Special Interest Group (TSIG), where interested people or organisation can apply.

The web page also provides links to social media and a way to join the mailing list.

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Visibility of Website

To ensure the effectiveness of the website, it has been designed and structured so it is shown in the first results for different search engines. This is quite important to allow easy access to the project to stakeholders that are looking for the project online.

During this reporting period, the website had a total of 1.371 visits, and users spend on average 1:17mins on the website, which is satisfactory and adequate to read most of the content available in each page.

Figure 2 Google Analytics for the 2nd Reporting period

Through social media, many visitors that are interested in the profile and want to get more information in a website, for this reason all the social media channels have access to the public project's website

2.2 NEWSLETTER

Purpose

The main purpose of the newsletter is to provide updated information related to the development of the project, including milestones and other activities performed within the project.

The different news has been published whenever there was relevant information or important progress.

These newsletters are addressed to those that are interested in the project and want to be informed about all the progress in the project. They provide in depth information related to the progress in a specific area of the project

Structure

The structure of each newsletter is modified depending on the needs of each issue.

The main structure includes general information about the project: description of the project, purpose of the project, partners, duration, etc. This information is consistent in every issue of the newsletter. The rest of the content is organised depending on the information to be published in each specific issue. The basic structure is presented in the template bellow (Figure 4).

Related to the web version of the newsletter is presented based on the website structure in the news section. Including all the information and with pictures, diagrams, etc. to illustrate the information presented.

Figure 3 Newsletters in Website

The published newsletters are the following:

- New methodology to accelerate innovation in the player sector.
- FabLab Bucharest at Maker Fair Vienna 2017
- AIJU participates in a workshop SAMT SUDOE: Manufacturing the future in the industry 4.0
- ToyLabs show off at the 16th International Trade fair for Toys & Preschool educational resources
- ToyLabs presented at the International Spielwarenmesse fair
- Workshops with companies at the Spielwarenmesse fair in Nuremberg
- ToyLabs on Maker Fair Berlin
- Last plenary meeting before the end of ToyLabs project
- TSIG workshop with Childhood experts in Bucharest

Figure 4 Newsletter Template

Distribution

The newsletters have been published in electronic format in all the cases, the main means has been through the website, where all the newsletters are available in the section news in the following link <http://toylabs.eu/posts-2-col> the latest and/or more relevant news are also showed in the main page of the site.

The second mean of distribution has been via e-mail to the interested stakeholders and through the internal contacts of each organization. The contacts made during the project have been kept for dissemination means, the list includes 58 FabLabs, 180 Toy Manufacturers from AIJU's database, 10 security experts and 5000 childhood experts and users through AIJU's family panel. After the GDPR came into force the e-mail distribution was terminated in order to reevaluate the effectiveness of the emailing channel.

The FabLabs contacted can be found in the following table:

Organization	Country
Fab Lab Moscow	Russia
Fab Lab Polytech	Russia
Fabricator	Ukraine

DAD-workshop	Poland
Hackerspace Lublin	Poland
HAMMERLAND Workshop	Poland
FabLab Kielce	Poland
FabLab Łódź	Poland
FabLab Budapest	Hungary
Smart Fab Lab	Bulgaria
FabLab Brno	Czech Republic
erfindergarden Munich	Germany
FabLab München	Germany
OpenLab	Germany
Fab Lab Region Nürnberg e.V.	Germany
FabLab Region Rothenburg o.d.T. e.V.	Germany
GarageLab Düsseldorf	Germany
Fab Lab Aachen at RWTH Aachen University	Germany
Happylab Berlin	Germany
ProDe	Montenegro
Fab.Lab Alto Minho	Portugal
Weproductise fablab	Portugal
FabLab IPB	Portugal
MILL - Makers In Little Lisbon	Portugal
FabLab Lisboa	Portugal
FabLab Graz	Austria
Happylab Salzburg	Austria
Happylab Vienna	Austria
Fablab Brussels	Belgium
OpenFab	Belgium
FabLab Zagreb	Croatia

Copenhagen Fablab	Denmark
Fablab Danmark	Denmark
Aalto Fablab	Finland
Fab Lab Oulu	Finland
8 FabLab Drôme	France
Artilect FabLab Toulouse	France
LABSud Montpellier	France
Habibi.Works	Greece
WeCreate Workspace	Ireland
Fab Lab Reykjavík	Iceland
Technoport FabLab	Luxembourg
Fablab Amsterdam	Netherlands
FabLab Arnhem	Netherlands
FabLab NTNU	Norway
FabLab Umeå University	Sweden
At3flo	Switzerland
FabLab Neuchâtel	Switzerland
Fablab Alicante	Spain
MADE Makerspace Barcelona	Spain
Fablab Bristol	United Kingdom
FabLab Essex	United Kingdom
Fab Lab London	United Kingdom

Table 1 Fablabs contacted

2.3 SOCIAL MEDIA

Various accounts in different social media channels were created by AIJU and NTUA at the start of the project. The maintenance of social media has been carried out by SingularLogic and AIJU.

Purpose

Having active social media channels helps disseminate the project to large audiences and increase awareness about the project between different target audiences.

Social media profiles have become the most direct and fast communication channel between the public and the organization, in this case the project consortium. Those interested in the project can easily ask for information or contact us in a more interactive way through the comments in a publication or even more directly via chat.

Apart from this, social media channels are the easiest way to keep the audience informed continuously about the project development.

Frequency and content

In order to be able to plan and schedule the publications in different social media the platform Buffer is being used. Through this platform is possible to schedule publications for the different social media channels so the content is consistent.

Social media post vary depending in the information to be shared. The content could be classified in shared articles, ToyLabs Blogpost, ToyLabs Events and other relevant information of the project. A general plan was scheduled in early phases of the project and has been updated based on the project development, this plan was a general guide that was modified when there was specific and relevant information to be shared.

Relevant posts have been boosted in order to reach larger audiences and ensure the visibility of the action, in particular the TSIG open call. The boosted post has been proven effective regarding the people reached.

Figure 5 TSIG boosted post

Followers and interactions

During the first 9 months of the project, ToyLabs achieved to establish an active presence, raise awareness for the project and engage a targeted audience.

The following table presents certain metrics regarding social media dissemination in the second reportin period of the project. The metrics as recorded are based on Facebook and Twitter presence.

Metric	Achieved
TOYLABS entries in the social media accounts	132
Social Media Followers	2.950
Likes	1.742
Impressions	16.151

Table 2 Social media metrics v1

The most crucial point to reach a successful dissemination rates, specially via social media channels, has been the release of the platform, together with the promotion of the various dissemination activities which have been performed in the fairs and exhibitions that ToyLabs partners participated.

Figure 6 Facebook Posts Likes

Figure 7 Facebook post Reach

2.4 TOYLABS BLOG

The blog posts are available in ToyLabs website www.toylabs.eu in the section news.

Purpose

Following with the aim of keeping the interested audience informed and involving new people in the project, a series of blog posts were created in the form of short news.

The blog posts intent to inform the audience on the different milestones and development of the project by giving specific information in an easy to access format so the different target groups, including non-professional, can easily follow with the project.

These pieces of news have been published regularly coinciding with the progress of the project. At every new step of the project a short description of the developments was prepared to be published.

Structure

ToyLabs blog was intended to reach a wide audience including a variety of target audiences (professional and non-professional). Therefore, the information had to be presented in a summarized and easy to understand manner. The information included is based on the most recent developments of the project, events participation, important milestones reached, etc.

All posts were accompanied with a picture, table or graphic to help illustrate the information presented in the article.

Frequency and responsible

All the posts were scheduled at the start of the project and a different responsible was established for each post according to the content. All partners have participated in the creation of the blog posts related to their tasks. The collection and publishing has been handled by NTUA.

The next table shows all the posts that have been posted and are available on the website and the responsible team for each one.

Title	Description	Date	Responsible
14. The Integrated ToyLabs Platform - V1	Things from D4.2	26/11/2017	SLG
15. ToyLabs Partner Matching and Selection Methodology	Input from T2.4	14/12/2017	NTUA
16. Walkthrough Of the ToyLabs paltform	Demo Scenario description	25/01/2018	SLG
17. Lessons Learned from 1st ToyLabs Demonstration period	Input from D5.2	14/02/2018	FABLAB LECCE
18. Presentation of the Final ToyLabs platform		29/03/2018	SLG
19. Final Lessons Learned from ToyLabs Demonstration period	Input from D5.3	30/05/2018	FABLAB LECCE
20. Outcomes and Key TakeAways from the ToyLabs project	Final outcomes of the project	28/06/2018	AIJU+NTUA

Table 3 Published Blogposts

Publishing

All the blogposts have been published in the news section of the website and the link was shared in social media to increase the reach.

In order to gather further attention and reach a bigger audience, all the blog posts have been shared in the different social media channels. These posts include a short and catchy description of the content of the blog and the link to the actual post in the website.

Figure 8 Blogs in website

2.5 TRADITIONAL MEDIA

Traditional media helps to reach the general public and provide information about the project and create awareness.

With traditional media such as newspapers, radio, etc. it is possible to reach a wide audience that will most probably include the target audiences for our project. In these press releases it is possible to provide general information to get people interested in the project and create awareness.

In this regard, the project was presented in two radio informative slots, two radio interviews and a press release in different printed and digital newspapers.

Regarding to the radio, the informative slots and interviews were broadcasted in RNE (Radio Nacional Española) and COPE, both national broadcasting services in Spain.

In the COPE interview, AIJU explained the main objectives of the project, the recent developments and the impact that this project would have in the toy sector.

In the RNE interview, Mr. Cesar Carrion from AIJU and Mr. Juan Antonio Maicas from JUEMA presented the project. Mr. Juan Antonio explained the impact that the project could have in Toy Manufacturing SMEs form JUEMA's firsthand experience with the project through the platform and Pilot cases.

Figure 9 Juan Antonio Maicas in the RNE Interview

Regarding the press release, an article was published in many different newspapers in their digital version and printed version for some of the cases.

The article presented on the first place a description of the project, including objectives, impact, and latest development. The release coincided with the project presentation in Nuremberg fair for this reason the information about the event was included to let people know about it. The Alicante region has a big concentration of Toy Manufacturers SMEs and most of them attend to the event every year, for this reason the inclusion of this information in a press release in this area was especially important.

The article was published and can be found in the following newspapers.

Media	Date	Link
Información	24/01/2018	https://www.diarioinformacion.com/alcoy/2018/01/24/aiju-reducira-tiempo-lanzamiento-juguetes/1980853.html
ARAMULTIMEDIA	-	http://www.aramultimedia.com/ca/societat/aiju-segueix_innova_n_en_un_projecte_per_a_pod_er_reduir_el_temps_de_llancament_dels_jogu_ets_al_mercat-27886.html
Radio IBI	-	http://www.radioibi.com/noticia.asp?idnoticia=108224
Ve. Valencia económica	-	http://valenciaeconomica.com/aiju-participa-en-un-proyecto-que-reducira-el-tiempo-de-lanzamiento-de-un-juguete-al-mercado/
Intercomarcal	-	http://www.intercomarcal.com/noticias/IBI/aiju-participa-en-un-proyecto-que-reducir%C3%A1-el-tiempo-de-lanzamiento-de-un-juguete/84353.html
Economia 3	17/01/2018	https://economia3.com/2018/01/17/130050-aiju-toylabs-proyecto-reducira-tiempo-lanzamiento-juguete/?platform=hootsuite
JUEGUETES B2B	23/01/2018	http://www.juguetesb2b.com/noticias/20180118/plataforma-toylabs-reducira-50-proceso-creacion-juguete.aspx

Table 4 press release

2.6 COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

The communication material is an easy way to provide instant information about the project, it is useful in fairs and events where the different materials help to bring attention to the project and give information to those interested, the main point is to give essential information to make people aware of the project and the work that is being done and contact information including the website where more in depth information can be found.

In order to provide suitable information for the different target audiences and provide information that really interests to those contacted, different versions and materials have been created. These materials have been adapted not only to the target audience but also to the type of event where they were meant to be used.

For this same reason, as the project has many target audience groups with different interests in the project, the dissemination material has been created so it can be easily modified and the information can be adapted to each case.

Brochures factsheets and banners

As explained before, the materials have been created for a specific event focusing on the event itself and the target audience it was directed to. The objective of these materials is to offer clear information on general aspects of the project with the purpose of impacting the audience and get them interested in the project. The information presented offers a basic description of the project development and goals always referring to a specific target.

The reason why different versions have been created is to be able to adapt the information to the interest of a specific target group as well as to the event characteristics in order to be able to offer effective information in each particular case.

During the second reporting period two new brochures were designed to reach toy manufacturers and FabLabs or creators respectively. These brochures are described in the next pages, including pictures of the design.

The third brochure (Figure 10) was created specifically for the Nuremberg Toy Fair; therefore, the brochure is mainly addressed to toy manufacturers. During the fair many Toy Manufacturers were contacted and they received more information about the project, with these brochures they were able to keep the details and contact information with them and find more details. This brochure highlights the main benefits the platform offers the toy manufacturing industries and how SMEs can take advantage of the new methodology in their business.

These brochures were handed personally to all the toy manufacturers contacted as well as placed in strategic locations in the fair such as the Toy Business Forum stand and JUEMA and V-Cubes' stands (Figure 11). The Toy Business Forum is located in the trend gallery area of the fair which ensures a big visibility of the project.

Figure 10 Nuremberg Brochure

Figure 11 Brochure placement in Toy Business Forum

The fourth and last brochure (Figure 12) for the project was prepared for the Maker Fair in Berlin, this version was mainly addressed to FabLabs and creators. The information provided is focused on how can FabLabs and Creators participate a new methodology of toy development. The objective was to present the information in an attractive manner to attract people and provide them further information about the project objectives and development.

These brochures were handed personally to those interested in the project and to all the people contacted during the fair (Figure 13). Also, the brochures were placed in different points at the fair such as the information stand and the presentation room.

Figure 12 Brochure for Berlin MakerFair

Figure 13 Berlin Maker Fair brochure placement

Poster & Roll up

During the first reporting period, a poster and rollup were created in order to stand out in the different events and grab assistants attention

Following the same objective, these materials were used in different events during the second reporting period.

One example is the roll up that has been used in events and meetings such as the project presentation in the Nuremberg Toy Fair Business Forum, the TSiG workshop carried out in Bucharest, etc.

Figure 14 ToyLabs rollup

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Promotional material

The promotional materials were created in order to be used in events as small gifts to attendants or to showcase the project in a less conventional way. These materials are effective to expand the communication exposure, to create awareness of the project and to build a consolidated relationship with stakeholders.

In order to have materials to promote the project and help people remember the project the next items were created during the second reporting period.

FabLab Romania prepared more keychains to be given in fairs and events as well as to keep promotional material in all partners' offices. These keychains were designed early in the project and have been used in many occasions such as the Berlin Maker Faire and the TSIG workshop.

JUEMA with the help of the FabLabs developed these figures in bright colors that were used as gifts in events and for the TSIG members attending to the workshop in Bucharest. FabLabs collaborated with the designs adapting them to roto-molding manufacturing technologies and JUEMA carried on with the production. The objects are a little doll with a heart, a hanging ornament and a phone holder all stamped with the ToyLabs logo.

Figure 15 Promotional material 2

The last promotional item created in the project has been a series of USB sticks (Figure 16) with the ToyLabs logo on them. These were used to thank the TSIG members for their assistance to the workshop organized in Bucharest. The USB sticks also included a series of interesting documents for them related to the project such as a brief presentation of the project and all the materials presented during the workshop so they could have this for future reference.

The selection of an USB stick was based on usefulness, quality and attractiveness, attributes that the recipients appreciate and helps to establish a consolidated relationship between TSIG members and the project.

Figure 16 Promotional material USB stick

Video

The objective of the promotional video is to inform and create awareness of the project. The audio-visual format helps to transmit a message in an easy and more direct way, besides it is a great way to grab people attention and make them remember the project. The videos offer interesting content that help people to better understand the project and the platform.

With this objective, the first video (Figure 17) presents the basic information of the project. It was decided to create a white board animation video to present the project in a dynamic way.

The video presents the main objective of the project and how we are going to achieve it. It introduces the new participants in the toy development process and how the different modules in the platform will help to bring better toys to the market in a shorter time.

This video is available on the project's YouTube channel in the following link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC00L5PmKnukMMSYQgKBgRfw> and has been shared several times in social media to reach more impact.

Figure 17 Promotional video

The second video presents an audio-visual demonstration of the platform. It shows the final result of the project, the modules in the platform and the main functionalities.

This video works as a walkthrough of the platform, this sort of tutorial will be based on the information presented in Deliverable D5.3. Updated Pilot Scenarios Execution and pilots Evaluation – final version, Section 5. WALKTHROUGH for the UTILISATION of the ToyLabs Platform where all the sections, modules and functionalities are explained and described to offer a very detailed information on how to use the platform and all the steps to be done to utilise it. However, the information in the video is presented in a dynamic way to offer a quick overview of the main things to consider when using the platform, the detailed information has been skipped in the video to avoid confusions and to keep it simple.

The objective of this video is on the one hand to help users better understand the platform before using it and avoid doubts, mistakes and other problems and on the other hand encourage people to start using the platform for the first time since they will be able to see how useful and easy can this new tool be.

The video is available in the ToyLabs' YouTube channel and in the platform as a step of the training process.

<https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC00L5PmKnukMMSYQgKBgRfw>

3 DISSEMINATION MECHANISMS

3.1. ORGANISATION OF PROJECT EVENTS

After the platform is ready to be released and almost all the components are implemented and functional, the project organised a series of workshops to instruct the different stakeholders in the new methodology, the functioning of the platform and all the benefits that come along with the participation in this project.

Different workshops and Demo events were organised to reach the different stakeholders of the project. These events were planned to be very interactive, so the participants would not only learn more about the platform but also experience how this new methodology would affect their own interests.

These events have also helped the consortium to fix bugs and some usability issues from the platform that were discovered while people participating in the workshops had the chance to use the platform.

Workshops and demos in Spielwarenmesse - Nuremberg JUEMA – V-Cubes

Two of the partners in the consortium, V-Cubes and JUEMA as Paola Reina were exhibitors in the Nuremberg Toy Fair Spielwarenmesse 2018, they saved a space and time in their booths to organise there the ToyLabs Workshops. The workshops took place on February 2nd 2018 at 14:00 in V-Cubes booth and at 12:00 at Paola Reina's booth.

Figure 18 Workshop poster

Due to the very different toy categories of these two companies their both in the fair were far apart. For this reason, it was decided to hold two ToyLabs Workshops during the fair in their booths in order to reach a wider audience and give the opportunity to companies dedicated to different toy categories to attend.

Figure 19 Workshop JUEMA

The workshops started with a general presentation of the project focusing on the impact for Toy manufacturers (the main audience of the events) followed with a demonstration of the platform use and the different modules.

The first part of the workshop consisted in a demo event, at this point the platform was presented following a walkthrough to show and explain all the modules and functionalities of the platform. With this demo the participants learnt how they could start a new product in the platform and how to follow all the steps using the different modules to be able to finish the process with a better product and cutting on time and costs based on the traditional method.

After the demo event those participants interested had the chance to experience the platform and the methodology and have consultations for each particular case.

During both workshops the ToyLabs team obtained an enriching feedback on the platform usability that allowed to evolve the platform in order to improve its adaptation to the toy SMEs and facilitate their management.

Figure 20 Workshop V-Cubes

The participation of both FabLabs became very important to show how through the platform it is possible to make prototypes in a fast way and with the use of new materials, allowing, at the same time, the contribution of useful recommendations about toy designs and materials.

Workshop TSIG Bucharest

In order to present the last version of the platform and all the implemented modules new functionalities, it was decided to organise an event dedicated to childhood experts form the TSIG. The event took place on the 30th of May 2018 in Bucharest.

The participants in the TSIG workshop are detailed in the table below (Table 5 TSIG members Workshop)

Although all the members of the TSIG were already aware of the project the workshop started with a presentation of the project so the participants had a better understanding of the it as a whole and the latest developments continued with a brief description of the tasks and activities to be performed during the workshop. Following this, there was an online demonstration of the new features incorporated to the platform and a training on how to use the AR engine, this brought a short discussion regarding some questions from the participants.

After a short break, the experts had some time to test the new features of the platform and solve any doubts they might have. During this part some bugs and usability issues were pointed out by the experts, this helped the consortium fix any problem to be able to create a really useful tool.

Agenda of the TSIG Workshop

Time <	Issue	Responsible
9.00 – 9.15	Welcome Partners & Experts	
9.15 – 9.45	Partners and TSIG presentation	AIJU + ALL
9.45 – 10.00	Session Plan	AIJU
10.00 - 10.20	Platform Training	SILO
10.20 – 10.30	Platform Login demonstration & TSIG login	SILO
9.00 – 9.15	Welcome Partners & Experts	
9.15 – 9.45	Partners and TSIG presentation	AIJU + ALL
9.45 – 10.00	Session Plan	AIJU
10.00 - 10.20	Platform Training	SILO
10.20 – 10.30	Platform Login demonstration & TSIG login	SILO

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No [Number].

Figure 21 TSIG workshop agenda

Figure 22 TSIG workshop in Bucharest

Afterwards there was a discussion and brainstorming session between the experts and project partners related to the main aspects of the platform, usability, added value, etc. this would help bring ideas and consider the different opinions that may come from the different expertise.

To finalise the event, the experts had to fill a questionnaire about the project and platform where they could give their expert opinion and help the consortium develop the best platform possible. More results regarding this event can be found in Deliverable 5.3 Section 4.4 Childhood Experts Evaluation The general results showed that the event was successful and interesting for the experts.

During the event, all the participants received an USB stick engraved with ToyLabs logo with different documents, including a project presentation and all the materials used during the workshop to be used as future reference. Also the keychains prepared by FabLab Bucharest and the figures prepared by JUEMA were delivered among the experts who appreciated the gesture.

Name	Expertise	Nationality
Úrsula Perona	Psychologist expert in children	Spain
Lucia Perez	Psychologist expert in disabilities	Spain
Altin Lubonja	Toys and Books Publisher and Distributor	Greece
Iliana Morelli	Montessori and coding educator	Italy
Istvan Csucsak	Toys Publisher and Distributor	Romania
Nagy Gábor	Toys Publisher and Distributor	Romania
Becky Hellwing	Child Psychologist and Family Psychotherapist	Germany
Teodora Maravela	Psychologist expert in children and disabilities - School	Romania
Anca David	Psychologist expert in children and disabilities - School	Romania

Table 5 TSIG members Workshop

Enabling an Open Innovation Model for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co -Creation with FabLabs, Safety
Experts and Customer Communities
WP6- Dissemination Communication and Community Engagement
Deliverable D6.2: "First Dissemination Communication and Community Engagement Report and Updated Plan"

3.2. PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS

Representatives from the consortium have attended different events since the start of the project to ensure contact with external parties and make them aware of the project and its purpose. The dissemination carried out in each event has varied depending on the type of event and the stage of the project. The events are selected according to the main topic and the assistants' profiles.

From the start of the project participation to events has been of a great relevance for the dissemination purposes. It offers us a direct contact with potential users of the platform and allows to fully explain the project and get their interest fast. The most important part of being able to have a real conversation with potential users is that it allows to personalise all the information to every particular case. In particular talking about ToyLabs, the project has many different stakeholders and each one of them has a very different reason to join us. During events it was easy to personalise the information offered and understand the public in order to explain the exact ways in which ToyLabs can benefit their business.

During the second reporting period, the participation in events has been carefully planned in order to reach the biggest number of potential uses. For this reason, the events selected are the Nuremberg Spielwarenmesse where almost every toy company is present and the Berlin Maker Faire where it is possible to find a big number of FabLabs and creators. In the following pages both events are detailed and all the activities performed are explained.

Spielwarenmesse 2018

Event information

Title: *Spielwarenmesse 2018*

Date/Place: Messezentrum Nuremberg, Nuremberg, Germany – 31st of January/4th February 2018

Participation: AIJU, NTUA, FabLab Lecce, FabLab Bucharest, SingularLogic, V-Cubes, JUEMA (Paola Reina)

Material: Presentation, Video, Brochure, Poster and Rollup

Action: Presentation of the project in the Toy Business Forum

Presented by Cesar Carrion (AIJU)

Attendees: More than 70,000 visitors from 130 countries, almost 3000 exhibitors. Around 60 attendees to the project presentation

<https://www.spielwarenmesse.de/fair/fair-profile/language/1/>

On February 1, 2018, AIJU, as coordinator of the H2020 ToyLabs project, presented the paper "TOLABS: New methodologies to reduce time to market" within the Toy Business Forum of Nuremberg.

During this presentation at the Toy Fair Spielwarenmesse, the participants were informed of the new business model proposed by ToyLabs that supports creativity models and production cycles of SMEs in the toy industry.

Cesar Carrion explained the overall goal of the project. The platform was introduced as well as the methodology based on co-creation and user validation in all phases, starting with an analysis of comments from customers and experts around a specific word or toy and the possibility to obtain early feedback, recommendations for improvement and possible concerns.

The platform was in the validation stages with the toy

companies JUEMA and V-CUBES, it was explained how the expectations are to reduce the launch time of a toy by up to 50%, from the concept definition phase to the final implementation in the market.

The toy manufacturers and designers that attended the conference showed great interest in the proposed methodology and the platform. After the presentation many attendees

approached to show interest and solve several doubts.

Later in the event, all partners visited different toy companies in the fair to present the project and offer further information. All the contacts were kept to offer further information in the future.

Meanwhile JUEMA (present in the event as Paola Reina) and V-Cubes presented the project in their company booths where they had brochures available and posters. The project was introduced to all the visitors to their booth that could become potential users of the platform or showed any interest.

During the participation in this event two workshops and demo events were performed in the partners' booth, to find more information related to this see Section 3.1 Organisation of project events.

Berlin MakerFaire 2018

Event information

Title: *Berlin Maker Fairer 2018*

Date/Place: FEZ Berlin 26-27 May 2018

Participation: AIJU, FabLab Bucharest

Material: Presentation, Video, Brochure, Keychains and Poster.

Action: Presentation of the project

Presented by Ina Dimitriu (FabLab Bucharest)

Attendees: Total of 15.200. 30 attendees to project presentation.

<https://maker-faire.de/berlin/>

These faires are meant for "Makers" – people interested in technology, manufacture and making things on their own. Pople that would join or start a FabLab but also engage in entrepreneurial activities. All Maker Fairs that FabLab Romania has visited has a few of makers who want to sell a toy or game. These makers have the concept of their toy, they know how to make it, but lack knowledge of standards, need help from experts and need knowledge regarding the market they are just trying to enter.

Because of the wide range of interests makers have, exhibitors were as diverse as teachers, product developers, retailers, DIY jewelry or cosplay makers, FabLabs and hackerspaces. We talked to

them about the ToyLabs project in order to collect feedback about the general idea of the project (to see if they found the platform interesting); and to welcome other FabLabs, DIY experts and small scale toy manufacturers to the platform. We showed them the platform and how it works using mobile phones.

Dissemination material, in the shape of flyers and keychains was given to those interested in the project. Flyers presenting the ToyLabs project were also placed in key points around the fair: main info point for the event and flyer stands. Both AIJU and FabLab Romania talked to both exhibitors and visitors at the fair and gave away flyers. While FabLab Romania talked mainly to other FabLabs and talked about the manufacturing opportunities, AIJU gave an insight to the toy industry and also acted as a standards expert, answering questions regarding toy making initiatives.

FabLab Romania also held a presentation in one of the amphitheatres. Presenting the platform, the general concept and how the platform can help those just starting out with a toy idea as well as how the platform can engage other FabLabs and help grow the maker community.

During the presentation the attendees showed great interest on the project and their will to participate in a project like this. Some of the participants had questions regarding the methodology and how could they participate in such a platform and all the doubts were solved.

After this event, it is expected to have more people join the platform and start using it.

3.3 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Scientific publications allow an effective dissemination of the project results and development to more specific target groups, particularly specialized and expert audiences of the different sectors participating in ToyLabs project.

Conference papers

NTUA has prepared and submitted the following conference papers:

- "Empowering product co-creation approaches through Business Interoperability Concepts: The Toy Industry case", 9th International Conference on Interoperability for Enterprise Systems and Applications (IESA 2018) to be held on 22/3/2018 and 23/3/2018 in Berlin.
This paper presented the Partner Matching methodology of the ToyLabs solution focusing on Business Process Interoperability as an enabler for any such procedure. Given that in the ToyLabs platform the stakeholders come from different business domains, this paper focused on the creation of a common vocabulary to make cooperation in the platform possible. This paper has already been accepted and presented.
- "A new paradigm for digital collaboration in the toy industry: empowering user co-creation through social media channels"
The second paper written for the project presented the Market Trends and Social Feedback component of the platform. The paper aimed to show that Social Media channels through data mining and sentiment analysis techniques can help companies uncover trends and gain feedback about their products. This paper has already been accepted.
- "Collaborative creation, production and distribution of new products in the toy industry: The ToyLabs Platform"
This paper presented the ToyLabs platform as the end-result of the project. It focuses on the challenges that SMEs in the EU toy industry are facing and presents the platform as an effective potential solution for defragmenting the market and helping SMEs regain their competitive advantage by also providing them with innovative tools and collaboration opportunities.

The following table offers further information related to the published papers:

Type of publication	Conference paper	Conference paper	Conference paper
Title	Empowering product co-creation approaches through Business Interoperability Concepts: The Toy Industry case	A new paradigm for digital collaboration in the toy industry: empowering user co-creation through social media channels	Collaborative creation, production and distribution of new products in the toy industry: The ToyLabs Platform
Authors	A.Michalitsi-Psarrou S. Koussouris C. Kontzinos O. Markaki C. Ntanos D. Panopoulos J. Psarras	C. Kontzinos A.Michalitsi-Psarrou O. Markaki C. Ntanos J. Psarras	C. Kontzinos A.Michalitsi-Psarrou C. Ntanos J. Psarras
Publisher	Springer International Publishing	Edition Donau-Universität	Taylor & Francis Group
Place of publication	Cham, Germany	Krems, Austria	Abingdon, UK
Year of publication	2018	2018	2018
Available in open access?	No	No	No
Peer-reviewed publication?	Yes	Yes	Yes
Joint public/private publication?	No	No	No

Table 6 Scientific Publications

Industry magazines

AIJU PARTICIPA EN UN PROYECTO QUE REDUCIRÁ EL TIEMPO DE LANZAMIENTO DE UN JUGUETE AL MERCADO

An article has been published in toy industry magazines and economical magazines. This article allowed to reach most of the toy manufacturers in the Valencian Community area and around Spain as a very important stakeholder of the project.

The article with the title "Aiju participa en un proyecto que reducirá el tiempo de lanzamiento de un juguete al mercado" explains how ToyLabs is creating a platform and a methodology that can transform the toy manufacturing process offering SMEs a new tool to update their processes and be able to get toys to the market in a shorter time by using the collaborative platform and with more certainty that this toy will be accepted in the market thanks to the experts and users participation in the process and the trend and sentiment analysis module.

Media	Date	Link
Ve. Valencia económica	-	http://valenciaeconomica.com/aiju-participa-en-un-proyecto-que-reducira-el-tiempo-de-lanzamiento-de-un-juguete-al-mercado/
Economia 3	17/01/2018	https://economia3.com/2018/01/17/130050-aiju-toylabs-proyecto-reducira-tiempo-lanzamiento-juguete/?platform=hootsuite
JUEGUETES B2B	23/01/2018	http://www.jugetesb2b.com/noticias/20180118/plataforma-toylabs-reducira-50-proceso-creacion-juguete.aspx
INTEREMPRESAS	26/01/2018	https://www.interempresas.net/Plastico/Articulos/207624-Aiju-participa-en-proyecto-que-reducira-tiempo-de-lanzamiento-de-juguete-al-mercado.html

Table 7 Industry magazines

TOYLABS: NEW METHODOLOGIES TO REDUCE TIME TO MARKET.

The conference performed in Spielwarenmesse, the toy trade fair in Nuremberg was accompanied with a paper in the fair magazine.

The article presents the project and details how is this project going to change the toy development process by offering SMEs the tool and methodology to reduce time to market and bring better toys thank to the collaboration of experts through all the process.

The abstract present in the paper is the following

The manufacturing companies, the distributors and inventors, will learn in this conference new methodologies to introduce toys in the market in a fast way, reduce costs and times in the development process of new products; and achieve greater success in the market. Direct tangible examples of the platform use will be presented. In addition, it will be possible to get contacts and information to collaborate on this platform for toy innovation.

The article is not available on line, attached in ANNEX 1 is possible to read all the article.

3.4 COMMUNITY BUILDING/ ENGAGEMENT WITH STAKEHOLDERS

The different target audiences have different interests in the project and need specific information, for this reason, all the dissemination and communication activities are carefully planned in order to reach to every stakeholder in the appropriate way to meet their expectative.

Each of the partners has dedicated their assistance to events to contact to a specific profile, mainly matching their own profile, that is for example toy manufacturers have mainly contacted other toy manufacturers.

Overall the contacts with stakeholders have been successful and the number of interested organisation and individuals has potentially increased thanks to the different communication and dissemination activities. After the release of the platform the interest in the different stakeholders increased and the communication resulted more effective.

At the start of the project AIJU performed over questionnaires and 13 personal interviews with toy manufacturers with the aim of learning the main problems of the SMEs in the sector. The main objective of these interviews was to gather information for WP1 in the D1.1 *Exploring Progress and Innovation in ToyLabs Tackled Domains And Concept Definition* but it also brought the opportunity to discuss with toy manufacturers about the project and inform them at a very early stage of the project about the objectives of the project and the expected impact for the industry.

During the progress of the project the main contact point with stakeholders has been the participation in events, where face-to-face meetings with interested visitors has given the opportunity to provide enough personalized information. During the events partners had the opportunity to explain the project and contact potential users to inform them about the platform and get them interested in the project.

As it has been explained previously the consortium organised workshops and demo events during some of the main events attended, this ordered the most effective way to validate results with the key stakeholders.

To create a network of potential users, once the platform had been released, stakeholders were contacted via e-mail to offer them more information on the latest developments of the project and invite them to join the platform and start getting benefit from the services offered.

3.5 SYNERGIES WITH PROJECTS

The objective of creating synergies with other projects is to encourage the knowledge exchange and mutual validation of results.

Projects with Synergies

IBUS

The overall objective for iBUS is to develop and demonstrate an innovative business model, based in the current supply chain, that boost the sells of the manufacturers of traditional toys of the European Union (EU) by using technologies Internet based, focusing in safe and high quality personalised products.

The project is coordinated by the Limerick University (Ireland) and the participation of enterprises and centres from Germany, France, U.K. and Spain. To highlight the presence of two Spanish toy enterprises, JUGUETTOS CENTRAL DE COMPRAS & FABRICA DE JUGUETES, that will be key in the determination of the iBus platform requirements and the sell and manufacturing of personalised toys through this platform.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 646167.

You can have further information at: www.h2020ibus.eu

AIJU is working on WP3 "Customised Product Design Virtual Environment" where we are supporting Design process developing a AR Tool. ToyLabs platform was presented to consortium and AR Module was introduced as a reference about how to collaborate between End User, Experts and Designers.

INNOVATION PROJECTS IN AIJU

API4TOYS

This project focuses on the integration of the videogame world within the traditional toy through the generation of common communication protocols (API) so that any video game developer is able to communicate with a traditional toy, capture information about the use of the toy, get communication with the same, and try to get the toy itself acquire a certain intelligence, "intelligence" aimed at obtaining learning methodologies adapted to each user, so that you can get to gamify learning in an adaptive way.

CLOUD4TOYS

Consists in the development of CLOUD environments for the use of electronic components and IoT technologies for the development of toys in the

sector. In addition, the CLOUD4TOYS operates in two different areas, on the one hand, the incorporation and improvement of connectivity in smart toy products; and on the other hand, the creation of a platform "in the cloud" adapted to the sector that allows to introduce the "Big Data" and the philosophy of the services in the cloud.

CYBERCLOUD4TOYS

A line of research is established that allows the creation of so-called intelligent toys adapted to the children's audience, in addition to allowing the collection of data within a controlled and safe environment for the user, providing the companies in the sector with the necessary patterns to improve later in the games and toys pedagogical proposals and providing experts with new tools to analyse behaviours, changes in habits and the child's evolution of the game.

Additionally, the project aims to generate a platform that complies with cybersecurity protocols to ensure users' use of advanced security and privacy standards.

What can be obtained from TOYLABS?

The TOYLABS Project has a collaborative platform in which different centres or institutions in Europe are located, so supporting the Platform developed in the CLOUD4TOYS with the TOYLABS platform would be very beneficial for the Spanish companies of the toy sector, since they could put in common knowledge or work methodologies with companies from the rest of Europe.

What can be transmitted from the Innovation Projects to the TOYLABS?

Of the 3 innovation projects, carried out by AIJU, TOYLABS can benefit from the creation of an API that facilitates the interaction of low cost electronic components with traditional toys (API4TOYS), as well as supporting its platform with the latest security and privacy tools and protocols to safeguard the information of your platform.

CUSTOMS TRENDS & KIDS

Custom Trends & Kids is a project coordinated by AIJU and funded by the regional government by the European fund for regional development. The complete name of this project is "Toy development by personalized trends methodologies during new product process".

The main objective of the Custom Trends & Kids project is to support Toys SMEs in the development of a new methodology to apply the Trend Knowledge

during the creation process of a new product. This necessity was detected during the interviews carried out with Toy companies in the WP1 of ToyLabs project.

The Market Analytics and Trends Analysis Component developed in the ToyLabs project will be very helpful to detect and validate new Toy Trends, giving more quantitative support and helping companies to have a deeper knowledge about trends, increasing their understanding of user needs and market evolution.

In addition, ToyLabs ICT tool promotes open innovation and contact with different experts, which could bring the opportunity to increase the collaboration between Trends experts and Toy companies.

SAMT SUDOE

SAMT SUDOE PROJECT aims at developing links and between enterprises, R&D centres, clusters, higher education and R&D+i governmental & regional institutions to promote new KET in SUDOE space.

In particular, the focus is to boost advanced productive systems through additive manufacturing and advanced materials including nanotechnology. Among its results there is a transnational collaborative platform that aims to ease the involvement of SMEs in R&D activities and collaboration among organisations.

PSYMBIOSYS

The PSYMBIOSYS project team presented the Sentiment Management Engine that was created as part of the project's Symbiotic Innovation Management Platform to provide insight into the technical and methodological foundations that would be useful in the design and implementation of the Market Trends and Social Feedback Analysis methodology of ToyLabs. Various informal meetings and calls took place between PSYMBIOSYS members, NTUA and SILO, including a presentation of the PSYMBIOSIS solution that also included AIJU.

Project "PSYMBIOSYS: Product-Service sYMBIOtic SYStems". PSYMBIOSYS aims at improving the competitiveness of European Manufacturing industries by developing an innovative product-service engineering environment, symbolized by a five-pointed symbiosis star – design-production, product-service, knowledge-sentiment, EDA-SOA, business-innovation – and able to dramatically reduce the time-to-market of more attractive and sustainable product-service solutions

INVENT

Reinventing the Distribution and Delivery of Personal Services through Cloud Apps and Marketplaces (INVENT, National) – INVENT focuses on the

generation of new knowledge to support the launch of innovative business models that capitalize the emergence of online marketplaces as intermediaries for distributing apps and cloud services.

PAASPORT

A Semantically-Enhanced Marketplace Of Interoperable Platform-As-A-Service Offerings For The Deployment And Migration Of Business Applications Of SMEs ([PAASPORT](#), FP7) – one of the primary objectives of PaasPort is to establish a pan-European Cloud marketplace, in order to provide the European Cloud PaaS vendors (in particular SMEs) the reference framework, and the enabling technologies and tools that will allow them to become part of a single, interoperable marketplace

NEMO

Hyper-Network for electroMobility ([NeMo](#), H2020) - NeMo will boost the market share of EVs by enabling increased accessibility to charging infrastructure, ICT services and wider B2B interconnectivity by creating common information models for objects, data and services.

CLOUDTEAMS

A strong synergy has been established between ToyLabs and CloudTeams project. Cloudteams is a H2020 project completed in 2017 (during the implementation of the ToyLabs project) in which SLG was one of the main actors.

CloudTeams "Collaborative Software Development Framework based on Trusted, Secure Cloud-based Pool of Users" targeted at creating a cloud-based platform transforming software development into a faster, collaborative and targeted process, by engaging communities of users who will participate in the product life cycle to help software teams develop better solutions for customers' problems.

Although CloudTeams refers to software products, while ToyLabs to tangible products (toys), both projects have as a target to enhance collaboration in the product development phases, as well as in early involve end-users in the process of validating a product before its final release. As Cloudteams and ToyLabs had two common partners (SLG and NTUA), collaboration and synergies between the teams implementing the two projects were established from the first day that ToyLabs project started to the last day that CloudTeams project finished and even afterwards in the framework of the post-exploitation activities of SLG for CloudTeams project. The synergies between the two projects were focused on the similar objectives they had, referring to two areas:

Structure and characteristics of an IT platform that can support product development in a collaborative manner

Development of methodological approaches for involving end-users in the product development process.

Joint activities

Event information

Title: El instituto tecnológico del juguete y 22 empresas investigan tendencias para innovar

Article

Date: 12/01/02018

<http://www.elmundo.es/comunidad-valenciana/alicante/2018/01/11/5a57b2ab46163f32698b461a.html>

<http://www.juguetesb2b.com/noticias/20180112/aiju-investiga-metodos-innovar-personalizando-tendencias-junto-22-empresas-valencianas.aspx>

EL INSTITUTO TECNOLÓGICO DEL JUGUETE Y 22 EMPRESAS INVESTIGAN TENDENCIAS PARA INNOVAR

Press release published in traditional media in electronic format, it was published in traditional newspapers and specialised magazines.

This article joins the projects Custom Trends&Kids and ToyLabs.

The article covers mainly two points:

- AIJU works on an effective method of assessment, adaptation and transfer of market trends, to improve the development of new toys
- The methodology will be embodied in a digital format and will include the bases of application of a guide of good practices

TOYLABS COLLABORATE WITH IBUS PROJECT IN DIFFERENT JOIN ACTIVITIES MENSUAL TELCO ON IBUS PROJECT

Event information

Title: Plenary Mensual Telco

Date/Place: September 2017 – Webex Session -IBI-SPAIN

Participation: AIJU

Material: presentation

Attendees: 25 participants form Ibus Consortium

www.h2020ibus.eu

Title: Technical Telco

Date/Place: June 2017 – Webex session - IBI-SPAIN

Participation: AIJU

Material: presentation, live demo

Attendees: 5 participants form Ibus Consortium

www.h2020ibus.eu

During 2017, TOYLABS AIJU Team share experiences with IBUS related to needs and developments in both projects.

From one side, EN71 requirements focused related to IBUS "Product Design Safety Evaluation Module "focused on WP3.

Focused on it, on September 2017, César Carrión shared information to IBUS consortium related to apply standard requirements rules in design in the monthly. This interaction between both projects allow us to grow on knowledge and focus how Standard requirements can help in design stages.

In June 2018 César Carrión collaborated in a technical Telco with IBUS WP3 Leader – PADERBORN UNIVERSITY - Ulrich Janke, TOYLABS AIJU Team shared with IBUS Team the TOYLABS Augmented Reality Module as a reference to development that they want to start on Task 3.8.

This first join activity is the beginning of a large connection during 2018 due IBUS project is starting now with the AR Tool that will visualize models in real-time from custom designs made by user through IBUS platform.

NTUA PRESENTED TOYLABS TO THE CHILDRESCUE PROJECT CONSORTIUM

Event information

Title: ChildRescue/ToyLabs
Teleconference

Date/Place: 14th June 2018/
Online Teleconference

Participation: NTUA

Material: Demonstration

Attendees: 20

ChildRescue is an EU funded project that aspires to effectively reduce the primary period between the moment a child is reported missing and the one when it is found, and to help predict and prevent the disappearance of Children in Migration, by increasing accuracy and timeliness of publicly and privately available information, by performing evidence-based predictions on the whereabouts of children in distress, and by providing location-based audience targeting of mobile alerts.

NTUA coordinates the ChildRescue project and intends to use the knowledge and experience from the Social Media analytics and Sentiment Analysis components of ToyLabs to

further the research on profiling techniques for missing children and unaccompanied migrant minors, aiming to reduce the time needed to locate a missing child and allow NGOs to predict which unaccompanied migrant minors may be in distress and what locations they may be more likely to be found.

At the same time, ChildRescue is being implemented with three pilot organisations and involves four high-profile NGOs in total, namely Missing Children Europe, Child Focus, the Hellenic Red Cross and Smile of the Child. ToyLabs was presented to the members of the ChildRescue Consortium to invite sociologists and childhood experts from these organisations to join the ToyLabs platform. As ChildRescue research, as well as some of the core activities of the scientists working for those NGOs, focus heavily on techniques to predict future behaviour patterns from observations of children, these childhood experts can be a very useful addition to the pool of experts in ToyLabs, when they apply behavioural analysis techniques during the evaluation of prototype testing sessions with children.

Exchange of results

All the developments in the ToyLabs platform have been shared in Github, a collaborative software development platform. All the developments are stored publicly in the account.

These developments are available in the site to be shared and the programming code is accessible to the public in the link <https://github.com/singularlogic/ToyLabs>

Figure 23 Github

3.6 INTERNAL DISSEMINATION

Internally, all partners have disseminated the project in their organizations and through the internal communication channels.

SingularLogic

Internal cross-country presentations were held in Romania & Greece to familiarize the company's marketing department and technical divisions about the ToyLabs business concept and technologies. Adequate input has been provided to the marketing department in order to prepare targeted campaigns that have been gradually launched in several corporate communication channels (website, intranet, company's social media, press releases). Internal workshops with the company's technical divisions were held in order to share technical know-how that can be used to commercial solutions.

Clustering with EU projects associated with the development of online marketplaces & ecosystems has been performed.

SingularLogic in collaboration with FabLab and Verdes Toys have targeted local toy manufacturing communities and 3d printing firms in Romania and Greece in order to disseminate the ToyLabs results. By approaching this network, SingularLogic has engaged users for the project's pilot operations and contribute in the building of the ToyLabs SME community.

NTUA

NTUA presented the ToyLabs project on the post-graduate course "Special Management Subjects" as part of a speak about business interoperability.

Moreover, information about the project has been uploaded to the Decision Support Systems laboratory website.

An active effort was made to promote the project to professionals and organizations that collaborate with the Decision Support Systems laboratory, aiming to create further synergies, spark up interest and contact potential users of the platform.

AIJU

Internal presentations have been held in order to inform the different departments about the project. Getting all the areas involved in the project and well informed of the progress leads to a more coherent work. Moreover, if all the departments are informed of the project they are able to disseminate the project to their interested contacts.

El proyecto TOYLABS se dio a conocer internacionalmente en la Feria SPIELWARENSESSE

El pasado 1 de febrero, AIJU como coordinador del proyecto H2020 ToyLabs, presentó dentro del Toy Business Forum de Nuremberg la ponencia "TOYLABS: New methodologies to reduce time to market".

Este proyecto, presentado en la feria internacional del Juguete Spielwarenmesse, respaldará los modelos de creatividad y ciclos de producción de las pymes de la industria del juguete.

La plataforma de ToyLabs pretende crear un nuevo método de creación del juguete basado en la validación del usuario en todas las fases, empezando con un análisis de comentarios de clientes y expertos entorno a una palabra o juguete.

ToyLabs permitirá proporcionar retroalimentación temprana, recomendaciones para mejorar y posibles preocupaciones, lo que ayudará a introducir en el mercado juguetes más adecuados y de mayor calidad y a reducir el tiempo de fabricación de los mismos y los costos.

La plataforma se encuentra actualmente en fase de validación con las empresas jugueteras INDUSTRIA AUXILIAR JUEMA, S.L. y V-CUBES, con unas expectativas de reducción del tiempo de lanzamiento de un juguete de hasta un 50%, desde su concepto hasta su puesta a punto en el mercado.

TOYLABS introduce nuevos actores en el proceso de desarrollo de producto tales como el análisis de las redes sociales como parte del análisis de tendencias, así como la participación de los FabLabs-talleres de fabricación digital.

Se puede obtener más información del proyecto a través de redes sociales o en la web oficial www.toylabs.eu.

El proyecto queda encuadrado dentro de la convocatoria Europea H2020-ICT-2016-2017 (Information and Communication Technologies Call) en el Tópico ICT-21-2016.

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AIJU launches its own Newsletter once every two months in both digital and printed versions. For the different issues, 700 copies are printed and distributed to partners, public entities and internal facilities and over 9.000 are sent by email to associate and non-associate professionals and companies in different countries (Spain, France, Italy, Germany, china, etc.). Since the start of the project this issues have included articles informing of the concept and progress of ToyLabs in total 9 articles related to ToyLabs. Apart from this, the organization website includes the link and description of ToyLabs in a section dedicated to projects. Through social media, AIJU's channels have shared ToyLabs information and posts.

V-CUBES

To promote the Project through the organization network, V-Cubes has published several Facebook and Twitter posts informing about the project and included information about the project in the organization website.

To directly promote the project, a personal e-mail was sent to 27 famous Toymakers in V-Cubes network informing about ToyLabs and asking to answer an on-line questionnaire about relevant and necessary information for the development of the project.

JUEMA

JUEMA is the manufacturing company associated to Paola Reina, given this, the project was presented to the different teams in both companies to ensure maximum diffusion in the company.

The main communication channels that have been used for internal communication belong to Paola Reina, as JUEMA being an industrial company has not many. The companies associated with JUEMA and Paola Reina were informed of the project and their feedback was gathered.

Using the internal channels JUEMA has contacted potential stakeholders and informed them about the project. Also during visits to their organization they have explained their participation in the ToyLabs project and the potential impact it could have in the toy industry.

FABLAB Lecce

Fablab Lecce has developed various activities and strategies aimed to spreading and engaging the community in the ToyLabs project.

We have sent an email to inform all our partners and customers what are the aims of the ToyLabs project .

We have spoken about the proget during the event "Conversazioni sul Futuro", an event

Four days with almost 200 special guests involved in about 90 appointment diffused in over 20 locations of Lecce (theatres, cultural centres, libraries, public place and schools) from Thursday the 26th to Sunday 29th October.

We have distributed some gadgets to advertise the ToyLabs Projects during the "Solidshow" event related to Innovation that will take place in Bari on November the 9th.

We are attending students from primary to high schools in the School@Work Program, period while the kids and teenagers go to company to understand better the workwolrd.

During this project, we involve them in the ToyLabs project by modelling and printing objects with the ToyLabs logo.

On the other hand, we use to host students from international schools who are attending some weeks of internship at FabLabs Lecce. Also those students are understanding the ToyLabs project, modelling and printing some items.

During those events some products with the ToyLabs logo printed on are realized and distributed during events and alternative projects.

FabLab Romania

In FabLab Romania, meetings have been performed to inform all the team about the project, it's stages and the expectations. The main dissemination activities performed have been related to plan and search suitable publication and events where the presentation of the project is interesting for the dissemination objectives.

The project has been presented to the clients in FabLab Romania facilities and all the visitors have been offered information through a mailing list.

Fablab Romania has reached several FabLabs to provide information about the project and gather feedback regarding their interest in participating in a project such ToyLabs.

Through the organisation social media all ToyLabs post have been shared and the internal dissemination activities were communicated.

ANNEX 1

CONFERENCE TITLE:

TOYLABS: New methodologies to reduce time to market.

SPEAKER: Mr. Cesar Carrión

Cesar Carrion: Expert in AIJU in Product Development and New Technologies. For more than 20 years he has collaborated with companies in the sector, advising and analysing the Development phase of new products for the toy sector. Actively participates in International Technological Congresses and Fairs. Currently PhD student in Artificial Intelligence.

SUMMARY FOR THE CONFERENCE DISEMINATION: The manufacturing companies, the distributors and inventors, will learn in this conference new methodologies to introduce toys in the market in a fast way, reduce costs and times in the development process of new products; and achieve greater success in the market. Direct tangible examples of the platform use will be presented. In addition, it will be possible to get contacts and information to collaborate on this platform for toy innovation.

TOYLABS: New methodologies to reduce time to market.

What is TOYLABS?

TOYLABS "Enabling an open Innovation MOdel for EU Toy Industry SMEs through Co-Creation with ToyLabs" (2016-2018) Horizonte 2020 (Nº expediente 732559) is a European project funded by the European Commission that aims to propose a new innovative business model for toy SMEs.

Pushing SMEs competitiveness

99% of the toy companies in Europe are SMEs that have to compete with new substitute products, low cost electronic materials, drones, educational robotics, augmented reality, etc. All this in an environment where the child end user increasingly reduces play time with traditional toys and spends more time with mobile phones, tablets, consoles and video games.

The traditional process of product development is running out of resources even in European areas where toy productive clusters have existed for years. There are very few specialized technicians, artists, sculptors, mould makers, auxiliary industry workshops, etc., on which the toy sector can rely on in those areas. And those that remain work slowly and costly, compared to the technologies that have emerged in recent times.

To increase the competitiveness of European SMEs, the sector must start using new technologies in its development process, incorporate them into its process, absorb its systematics and adapt it to improve its current processes.

Challenges on the road

The main obstacle that toy SMEs currently encounter is the lack of knowledge about technology and the great technological advances applicable to their sector. Some examples: Social Media Data Analysis as a starting point to analyse market trends; direct feedback from the user in the development process; design with CAD systems; printing prototypes using 3DPrinting; incorporation and adoption of Smart components on the products; use of Augmented Reality, Virtual Reality or immersive environments components; etc.

Another obstacle in innovation lies in market time. Anticipating is the key to success. The big companies are able to advance the processes and present novel products in October-November. While the small companies barely arrive at the fairs of January of the following year with novelties and thanks to an incredible effort. This fact causes that when they arrive at the fair, the big customers-buyers have already closed a large part of their orders with the big manufacturers, hindering the negotiation capacity of the European SMEs.

Despite this, it is surprising how the toy companies have evolved in the development of products and have managed to adapt, year after year to all the problems that have been found along the way. This project proposes to give them more tools to compete successfully in the market taking advantage of existing resources in Europe but often unknown to them.

Fablabs as a petrol station on the road

With the appearance of 3DPRINTING technologies and the first STARTUPS, a new concept of service company emerged, FABLABS, centres of innovation for prototype manufacturing.

This new type of companies is a clear opportunity for SMEs in the sector, being able to act as a link, advising them on the incorporation of the most appropriate new technologies for their process of creating innovative toys.

TOYLABS as a new methodology to reduce time to market

After consulting more than 40 companies in the sector in Europe, AIJU has detected that there is a need to change the current methodology of product

development and adapt it to new technologies, hence the configuration of TOYLABS. A tool for innovation in the sector to accelerate the process of reaching the market of games and toys.

TOYLABS is a collaborative work platform for the innovation in the process of developing new toys. To do so, it incorporates a new Social Networks Analysis Module with which the company can easily detect trends, relevant topics, user needs, etc. focused on each particular product.

TOYLABS also allows to incorporate the Experts in Safety Regulations in the early stages of the toy development process, thus anticipating the normative advice at the time of defining the toy concept, its first designs and applying it to its first prototype. This reduces costs and times as it anticipates problems before approaching production. TOYLABS will allow us to communicate with the said Regulation Experts from the first moment, still in the conceptual phase of the idea of a new toy.

Finally, TOYLABS incorporates a new augmented reality tool that will facilitate the work of previewing prototypes in 3D models.

From the conceptualization phase, any of the parties involved in the new development can upload or update different product designs (whether it is the complete product or simply some parts). At that same moment, the Experts that will participate in the validation can be selected, providing feedback on the design.

To facilitate participation, from the augmented reality module experts can preview the designs and provide feedback by filling in forms corresponding to questions of interest.

And the most important thing about TOYLABS is that the platform also incorporates a very reliable system of partner selection (Partner Matching) that will allow, after signing confidentiality contracts, selecting the right PARTNER in the process.

New Business Model also for Toy makers and Retailers (online and offline market).

The TOYLABS platform not only allows the toy manufacturer to shorten the time to the market, it also allows the manufacturer to be introduced as another element in the chain of development of new products.

With this formula, a new product development model is presented where anyone interested can be the developer of a new toy. From an online and offline store, a family, a school, a distributor, any entrepreneur can develop their own product for a particular event or to generate a business if they see the opportunity.

By signing up on the platform, even a person totally outside the world of the toy, can select partners that allow them to develop their idea. Another important aspect is that toy manufacturers can produce a short or promotional production for third parties in such a way that they increase their sales and production.

FabLabs play a crucial role, as a centre for collecting new ideas. TOYLABS has a network of FabLabs of European coverage so that practically from any country in Europe you can have an input to these developments of new products.

Who is working in TOYLABS

The project is coordinated by AIJU (Technological Institute for Children's Products and Leisure), which participates as Expert in social and toy market trends, Expert in End Users, Expert in the application of safety standards, as well as an expert in focused product development, to the sector and its value chain.

To develop the project, the consortium has a technical partner specialized in the development of collaborative platforms SINGULAR LOGIC S.A., and with a scientific partner expert in the Social Media data analytics, the National Technical University of Athens. The FABLABS from Italy (StartSmart) and Romania (Spot Design) participate actively in the demonstrators' part, which collaborate very actively with the European FABLABS network.

As representation of the toy sector the companies JUEMA (Spain), with their brand PAOLA REINA, and V-CUBES (Greece) are participating, the first in the development of dolls, and the second in the development of mechanical toys.

For more information about the project:

<http://toylabs.eu/>